

Improving Physical Fitness Learning Outcomes Through Circuit-Based Learning in Class X Students of Sman 22 Bone

Andi Muh. Ihsan Febri Amat¹, Ilham Kamaruddin², Ahmad Adil³, Muh. Adnan Hudain⁴, Suwardi⁵

^{1,2,3,4,5}Faculty of Physical Education and Sports Study Program, Postgraduate, Makassar State University, Indonesia

ARTICLE INFO

Published Online:

10 September 2025

Corresponding Author:

Andi Muh. Ihsan Febri
Amar

ABSTRACT

This research is quantitative research aimed at determining the Improvement of Physical Fitness Learning Outcomes Through Circuit-Based Learning in Class X Students of SMAN 22 Bone. The subjects of this study were 25 students of class X.A of SMAN 22 Bone. The data collection process in this classroom action research was carried out by testing. The test is the main research instrument used in collecting data to measure physical fitness using the Circuit learning model. Based on the results of the data and discussion, the results of the study in cycle I showed that the percentage of completion was 40% or 10 students got a score of ≥ 70 . Furthermore, in Cycle II, the first meeting experienced an increase, namely 96% or 25 students who got a score of ≥ 70 out of 25 students. At the second meeting of cycle II, the results were 96% or 24 students got a score of ≥ 70 out of 25 students overall. The indicators of research success that have been set in this study have been achieved. In this case, 24 or 96% of students have obtained a minimum score of 70 (sufficient). Based on the results of planning, implementation, observation, evaluation and reflection, it is concluded that this research has been successful, namely by achieving the indicators and answering the research hypothesis by using the circuit learning model to improve physical fitness in class X students of SMAN 22 Bone.

KEYWORDS: Physical Fitness, Circuit Based Learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Sports and health education is an integral part of overall education which aims to develop aspects of fitness, motor skills, critical thinking skills, social skills, reasoning, emotional stability, moral actions, aspects of lifestyle and introduction to a clean environment through selected physical, sports and health activities which are planned systematically in order to achieve national education goals. (Darmawan, I, 2017). Sports, as part of PJOK, function not only as a means of maintaining health and strengthening the body, but also as a medium for character development, strengthening social relationships, and increasing a sense of nationalism. According to (Dwicalhya & Arjuna, 2017) sports also play a role as a means of strengthening social relationships and forming individual character from an early age. Physical education at the high school level also plays a role in shaping students' character and personality. Through various structured physical activities, students can develop discipline, responsibility, and the ability to manage emotions and pressure in competition. Thus, educators are required to apply innovative and adaptive learning methods in order to motivate students and increase their participation in physical education activities. (Afdinda et al., 2021). With the right approach,

physical education at the high school level not only contributes to improving students' fitness and health, but also plays a role in forming a generation that has a strong mentality, is confident, and is able to work together in a wider social environment. Then according to (Arifin, Z, 2018) the physical fitness of a nation can be used as a benchmark to indicate its level of health. Physical fitness education for students is very important because it can increase their mobility to achieve academic achievement. Then according to (Purba et al., 2020) the physical fitness of a nation can be used as a benchmark to indicate its level of health. Physical fitness education for students is very important because it can increase their mobility to achieve academic achievement. This can be achieved through PJOK learning and extracurricular activities that maximize physical movement. To achieve optimal results, fitness improvement requires continuous and consistent exercise. Especially in schools, students can optimize their physical growth by exercising regularly. In the context of learning, it is important for teachers to choose the appropriate model so that learning objectives can be achieved optimally (Kamaruddin et al., 2022). One of the learning models that is considered effective in physical education is the circuit training learning model. To overcome these problems, an

effective, interesting learning model is needed that is appropriate to the needs of students. One approach that has proven effective is the circuit training learning model. This model involves a series of physical activities at several stations designed to train various fitness components such as strength, agility, endurance, and coordination. In addition to being flexible and efficient, this model is also able to increase student participation, cooperation, and motivation (Rachmawati, 2015). Various studies have shown the effectiveness of circuit training in improving students' physical fitness, both in intracurricular and extracurricular activities. The results of these studies strengthen the belief that the implementation of circuit training can be a solution to the low level of physical fitness of students (HAERUDDIN et al., 2023). In addition, the diagram learning model has advantages in terms of understanding and efficiency. Teachers can adjust the intensity, type of activity, and number of stations according to the abilities and needs of students. This makes the circuit diagram model suitable for use in various levels of education, including elementary and secondary schools. With a varied and fun approach, circuit learning can increase students' motivation to actively participate in physical education activities (Erik et al., 2023) stated that one of the easy physical exercise methods that does not require a long time is circuit training. This is the reason why this method is one of the best choices. Because when done, it can increase students' motivation to do the movement tasks that must be completed. Physical fitness is influenced by a person's level of physical activity (Kamaruddin et al., 2023). Each activity has a level of stability that if done routinely can have an impact on fitness. Physical activity is related to the cardiorespiratory fitness of children and adolescents. Some people have different levels of physical activity, depending on the type of activity they do. The development of each individual's physical fitness through sports aims to increase endurance and physical condition (Wibowo, 2018). Physical fitness is divided into two categories: health and skill component fitness (Supariyadi et al., 2022). The elements of physical fitness related to health are explained, namely: (1) body composition, (2) body flexibility and flexibility, (3) muscle strength, and (4) cardiorespiratory endurance. In addition to the components of physical fitness related to health, components of physical fitness related to skills are also needed, such as: (1) strength which is a person's ability to create tension (pressure) against a resistance. Success in completing different types of exercises is measured by sets or circuits. That is, each series consists of different types of exercises that must be completed individually. Circuit training trains the muscles of the arms, abdomen, back, and legs, which are part of the smash stroke. According to (Mohzana et al., 2023). a circuit training program should be designed by considering several important features. A short circuit typically consists of six to twelve exercises, with a total workout duration ranging from ten to thirty minutes, and is usually performed in three rounds. It is

essential to gradually increase the individual's physical demands. Moreover, the arrangement of exercises in the circuit should allow for alternating muscle use. The training plan should also take into account the duration or the number of repetitions performed. To improve the effectiveness of the training, one can either reduce the time needed to complete the circuit without changing the load or repetitions, or increase the load or the number of repetitions. In practice, there is approximately a two-minute rest period between circuits.

II. METHODS

This type of research is classroom action research (CAR) which is very useful for teachers to improve the quality of learning outcomes in the classroom. By implementing the CAR stages, teachers can use various relevant learning theories and techniques creatively to solve problems in their own classrooms, not in other people's classrooms. This research is planned for February 2024 to March 2025 at SMA Negeri 22 Bone, Jl. Tana Batue Village, Libureng District, Bone Regency, South Sulawesi Province. The subjects of this study were 25 students of class X.A of SMA Negeri 22 Bone. This classroom action research was designed in two cycles; the first cycle had 4 meetings, and the second cycle had 4 meetings. Each cycle consisted of several different stages, depending on the research objectives. The activities carried out in the second cycle were basically repeating or improving the activities carried out in the first cycle. The following figure shows the stages of the classroom action research cycle.

Figure 1 Arikunto, (2019) 's PTK Cycle

The classroom action research model consists of several interconnected stages. The planning stage involves explaining what, why, when, where, by whom, and how the research will be conducted. Following the planning stage is the implementation of the action, which is the execution of the previously prepared plan. During this process, observation is carried out to record various events that occur

throughout the implementation. The final stage is reflection, which involves reviewing the results of the observations and evaluating the actions taken through discussion. The outcomes of the observation and reflection stages can serve as the basis for designing the research program for the next cycle. The implementation of this research focuses on two aspects, namely the learning process by applying the circuit model and the results of learning physical fitness in class X students of SMAN 22 Bone.

1. process focus

The process focus is the activity of observing the process or events that occur in the learning process which includes the activities of teachers and students as well as the interaction of all elements during the implementation of the Circuit model in the physical fitness learning process for class X students of SMAN 22 Bone.

2. Results focus

This research will focus on learning outcomes, namely looking at the improvement in learning outcomes of class students after using the Circuit learning model through a research cycle and conducting assessments.

There are two variables in this study: one independent variable and one dependent variable, Independent variable of circuit model implementation. The implementation of circuit learning model is a learning model that involves various movements marked by several posts that have been provided according to what is to be achieved, presentation of material or understanding of the activities to be carried out, practicing according to the material, and calculating scores. The dependent variable for physical fitness learning outcomes, learning outcomes can be defined as the level of mastery and understanding of students in carrying out each movement in physical fitness, which is measured through a skill test that includes the technical aspects of sit-ups, squats, prones, climbers, shoulder tabs,

The data collection process in this classroom action research is carried out by testing. Tests are the main research instruments used in collecting data to measure physical fitness using the Circuit learning model. The tests given are cognitive, psychomotor, and affective tests. In this study, the test given to test these three aspects in students is a questionnaire containing questions, Steps to do sit-ups, squad trush, Prone, climber, shoulder tab, and things related to attitude. The researcher did this because he wanted to measure the level of ability and understanding of students regarding physical fitness. The focus of this study is to improve physical fitness using the circuit learning model of class X.A students of SMA Negeri 22 Bone.

Data analysis is carried out to process the learning outcomes in the research by following specific procedures. The first step is to calculate the average scores of students' psychomotor skills and cognitive tests. Next, a data distribution table is compiled, which includes the results of psychomotor and cognitive skill tests, covering research

subjects, highest scores, lowest scores, average scores, and standard deviation. After that, a category table is created based on the average scores, which are grouped into the following categories: very poor, poor, fair, sufficient, good, and very good.

The indicator of success in this classroom action research is the improvement of physical fitness through the implementation of the circuit learning model in Class X.A of SMA Negeri 22 Bone. According to the Minimum Mastery Criteria (KKM) set by the school, the minimum standard for individual mastery is a score of 70, and mastery is considered achieved classically if 80% of the students in Class X.A reach this standard. Additionally, the percentage of student activity is expected to increase in each cycle.

There is an increase in the average student learning scores in each cycle conducted. In addition, the level of student mastery on a classical scale shows satisfactory results, reaching more than 75% of the total number of students.

Class mastery is calculated using the formula

$$\frac{\text{(Number of Students Who Have Achieved Mastery)}}{\text{(Total Number of Students)}} \times 100\%$$

The indicators of success in assessing student learning outcomes based on the national standard KKTP 70 are explained as follows:

Table 1. Student Learning Outcome Completion Indicators

No	Score Range	Criteria	Description
1	> 91 – 100	Very Good	Mastered
2	> 79 – 90	Good	Mastered
3	≥ 70 – 78	Fair	Mastered
4	<70	Poor	Not Mastered

III. RESULTS

1. Description of Initial Condition (Pre-Cycle)

Before carrying out the action, the researcher and collaborator took initial research data. This was intended to determine the initial conditions of the class on the Physical Fitness material for Class X Students of SMAN 22 Bone. The description of the data taken is Physical Fitness for Class X Students of SMAN 22 Bone. The initial conditions of Physical Fitness for Class X Students of SMAN 22 Bone before being given Circuit-Based Learning for Class X Students of SMAN 22 Bone are presented in the following table:

Table 2. Initial Data Summary Results

N	Score Range	Criteria	Frequency	Percentage	Description
1	> 91 – 100	Very Good	0	0%	Mastered

2	> 79 - 90	Good	0	0%	Mastered
3	≥ 70 - 78	Fair	4	16%	Mastered
4	<70	Poor	21	84%	Not Mastered
Amount			25	100%	

Based on the table of initial observation results before the action was given, it can be explained that all students have not shown abilities in the good criteria and above. Therefore, an action was drawn up to improve the quality of Physical Fitness in Class X Students of SMAN 22 Bone, through a circuit-based learning model. The researcher planned 2 cycles, each cycle consisting of 4 stages, namely: (1) Planning, (2) Implementation, (3) Observation, (4) Reflection.

2. Cycle I Meeting 1

In this step, observations were made by researchers and collaborative teachers during the learning process. At this meeting, all students were present, there were 25 students in total. After the implementation process of the circuit-based learning model on physical fitness in class X students of SMAN 22 Bone. The following are the results of observations of physical fitness in class X students of SMAN 22 Bone which are assessed from three aspects, namely cognitive, psychomotor, and affective.

Table 3. Summary Results of Observations Cycle I Meeting I

N	Score	Criteria	Frequency	Percentage	Description
1	> 91 - 100	Very Good	0	0%	Mastered
2	> 79 - 90	Good	0	0%	Mastered
3	≥ 70 - 78	Fair	7	28%	Mastered
4	<70	Poor	18	72%	Not Mastered
Jumlah			25	100%	

Figure 2. Observation Graph Cycle I Meeting I

Based on the data above after implementing the circuit-based learning model at the first meeting, it shows that physical fitness in class X students of SMAN 22 Bone is 0 students (0%) in the very good category, 0 students (0%) in the good category, 7 students (28%) in the sufficient category and 18 students (72%) in the less category. So at the first meeting of cycle 1 there were 7 or 28% of students in the good category (complete) out of 25 students overall. So, it can be concluded that physical fitness in class X students of SMAN 22 Bone in cycle 1 carried out in research activities has increased by using the circuit-based learning model, but has not met the maximum standard of physical fitness in class X students of SMAN 22 Bone as expected by achieving the target standard category of good or ≥75% of students getting a score of ≥70 and above. The percentage of completion obtained in cycle I was 28% or 7 out of 25 students who got a score of ≥70. Thus, it is necessary to carry out the next cycle through a circuit-based learning model, by improving the process that has been implemented in the first cycle.

3. Cycle I Meeting II

In this step, observations were made by researchers during the learning process. At this meeting, all 25 students were present. After the implementation process of the circuit-based learning model in physical fitness learning for class X students of SMAN 22 Bone. The following are the results of observations of physical fitness in class X students of SMAN 22 Bone which are assessed from three aspects, namely cognitive, psychomotor, and affective.

Table 4. Summary Results of Observations Cycle I Meeting 2

N	Score	Criteria	Frequency	Percentage	Description
1	> 91 - 100	Very Good	0	0%	Mastered
2	> 79 - 90	Good	4	16%	Mastered

3	≥ 70 - 78	Fair	6	24%	Mastered
4	<70	Poor	15	60%	Not Mastered
Jumlah			25	100%	

Figure 3. Observation Graph Cycle I Meeting 2

Based on the data above after implementing the learning model at the second circuit-based meeting, it shows that physical fitness in class X students of SMAN 22 Bone is 0 students (0%) in the very good category, 4 students (16%) in the good category, 6 students (24%) in the sufficient category and 15 students (60%) in the less category. So at the second meeting of cycle 1 there were 10 or 40% of students in the good category (complete) out of 25 students overall. So, it can be concluded that physical fitness in class X students of SMAN 22 Bone in cycle 1 carried out in research activities has increased by using the circuit-based learning model, but has not met the maximum standard of physical fitness in class X students of SMAN 22 Bone as expected by achieving the target standard category of good or $\geq 75\%$ of students getting a score of ≥ 70 and above. The percentage of completion obtained in cycle I was 40% or 10 out of 25 students who got a score of ≥ 70 . Thus, it is necessary to carry out a second cycle through a circuit-based learning model, by improving the process that has been implemented in the first cycle.

4. Cycle II Meeting I

In this step, observations were made by researchers and collaborative teachers during the learning process. At this meeting, all students were present, there were 25 students in total. After the implementation process of the circuit-based learning model in physical fitness learning for class X students of SMAN 22 Bone. The following are the results of observations of physical fitness in class X students of SMAN 22 Bone which are assessed from three aspects, namely cognitive, psychomotor, and affective.

Table 5. Summary Results of Observations Cycle II Meeting I

N	Score	Kriteria	Frekuensi	Persentase	Deskripsi
1	> 91 - 100	Very Good	0	0%	Mastered
2	> 79 - 90	Good	10	40%	Mastered
3	≥ 70 - 78	Fair	8	32%	Mastered
4	<70	Poor	7	28%	Not Mastered
Jumlah			25	100%	

Figure 4. Observation Graph Cycle 2 Meeting I

Based on the data above after implementing the learning model at the circuit-based meeting of cycle 2, the first meeting showed that physical fitness in class X students of SMAN 22 Bone was 0 students (0%) in the very good category, 10 students (40%) in the good category, 8 students (32%) in the sufficient category and 7 students (28%) in the less category. So at the first meeting of cycle 2, there were 18 or 72% of students in the (complete) category out of 25 students overall.

5. Cycle II Meeting II

In this step, observations were made by researchers and collaborative teachers during the learning process. At this meeting, 25 students attended. After the implementation process of the circuit learning model in physical fitness learning for class X students of SMAN 22 Bone. The following are the results of observations of physical fitness in class X students of SMAN 22 Bone which are assessed from three aspects, namely cognitive, psychomotor, and affective.

Table 6. Summary Results of Observations Cycle II Meeting II

N o	Scor e Ran ge	Criter ia	Frequen cy	Percenta ge	Descripti on
1	> 91 - 100	Very Good	4	16%	Mastered
2	> 79 - 90	Good	20	80%	Mastered
3	≥ 70 - 78	Fair	0	0%	Mastered
4	<70	Poor	1	4%	Not Mastered
Jumlah			25	100%	

Figure 5. Observation Graph Cycle 2 Meeting 2

Based on the data above after implementing the circuit learning model in cycle 2, the second meeting showed that physical fitness in class X students of SMAN 22 Bone consisted of 4 students (16%) on a very good scale, 20 students (80%) on a good scale, 0 students (0%) on a sufficient scale. And 1 student (4%) on a less scale. So, at the second meeting of cycle II, the results obtained were 96% or 24 students obtained a score of ≥ 70 out of 25 students overall. The indicators of research success that have been set in this study have been achieved. In this case, 24 students or 96% have obtained a minimum score of 70 (Good). Therefore, from this study it can be concluded that physical fitness in class X students of SMAN 22 Bone can be increased by using the circuit learning model in class X students of SMAN 22 Bone.

IV. DISCUSSION

This classroom action uses a circuit learning model to improve physical fitness in class X students of SMAN 22 Bone. Before the teacher carries out the cycle 1 action, he must first prepare the things that are considered necessary in the implementation of cycle I meeting 1, namely preparing observation sheets, making lesson plans, preparing equipment in circuit learning. This study was attended by 25 students. The implementation of cycle 1 meeting 1 actions

began based on the phases in the circuit learning model, namely conveying learning objectives, presenting materials, organizing students in groups, guiding groups to work and study, evaluating, and giving awards. Based on observations and evaluations in cycle I, Learning outcomes Learning outcomes Physical fitness in class X students of SMAN 22 Bone have not reached the established success indicators, namely 75% of students who get a score of ≥ 70 or more. The percentage of completion obtained in cycle I was 40% or 10 people who completed it out of 25 students. Thus, the study was continued to the next cycle. Furthermore, in Cycle II, the results obtained were 96% or 24 students obtained a score of ≥ 70 out of 25 students overall. The indicators of research success that have been set in this study have been achieved. In this case, 24 or 96% of students have obtained a minimum score of 70 (sufficient). Based on the results of planning, implementation, observation, evaluation and reflection, it is concluded that this study has been successful, namely by achieving indicators and answering the research hypothesis by using the circuit learning model can improve Physical Fitness learning outcomes in class X students of SMAN 22 Bone. Circuit-based learning (circuit training) has been proven to be an effective method in improving Physical Fitness learning outcomes of students at various levels of education. Based on the results of a review of ten studies in the last five years, it was found that this approach was able to have a positive impact on various components of Physical Fitness learning outcomes, such as cardiorespiratory endurance, muscle strength, agility, and flexibility. Research by Putra and (Sulistiyono et al., 2022) in Semarang showed an increase in Physical Fitness learning outcomes after participating in a 12-day circuit training program. These results are in line with the findings of (Nahar et al., 2024) at SMA Negeri 3 Cirebon, which showed an increase of 28.19% in extracurricular basketball students. Both of these studies confirm that circuit learning can increase physical capacity in a relatively short time if designed systematically. Furthermore, research by (Pulungan et al., 2021) at MA Annur Nusa confirmed that the circuit training method is effective in physical education learning, especially in increasing the degree of Physical Fitness learning outcomes as a whole. In addition to improving physical aspects, this learning also fosters an attitude of cooperation and discipline in students in following the stages of training. Several other studies have highlighted the benefits of circuit training in developing more specific fitness components. For example, this exercise improves students' cardiovascular endurance (Haryanto et al., 2022), improves the body mass index of young athletes (Hudain et al., 2023), and increases students' motivation and participation in PJOK learning (Lestari et al., 2023) The success of this learning is associated with movement variations, controlled exercise intensity, and activity rotation patterns that make students active in turns without long breaks. Overall, it can be concluded that circuit-

based learning is an effective and efficient method to improve the Physical Fitness learning outcomes of students at various levels of education. The main advantages of this method lie in its flexibility, its ability to improve various fitness components simultaneously, and its ease of application in the school environment.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the data analysis in the previous discussion and the results of the Classroom Action Research that has been conducted, the author draws the following conclusions: There is a significant increase in the learning outcomes of Physical Fitness through Circuit-Based Learning in Class X Students of SMAN 22 Bone.

Based on the results of the discussion and conclusions obtained from this study, the author proposes several suggestions as follows:

1. Teachers

Teachers are expected to make interesting learning as an alternative in physical education subjects to improve learning outcomes and Physical Fitness learning outcomes and activate students in the learning process. Teachers as those in control of the teaching and learning process should carry out learning that involves activating students. One of them is through a circuit-based learning model.

2. Principal

The principal as the person in charge of education at the school should always provide motivation and facilities to teachers in order to improve the quality of education, especially in physical education subjects.

3. Students / Researchers

To the next researchers, who will study a similar formulation, it is hoped that they can develop this circuit-based learning model by studying learning in more depth.

REFERENCES

1. Afdinda, R., Saputra, E., & Iqroni, D. (2021). Kontribusi Pola Hidup Sehat dan Circuit Training Terhadap Hasil belajar Kebugaran jasmani. *Jurnal Olahraga & Kesehatan Indonesia*, 1(2), 136–142.
2. Arifin, Z. (2018). Pengaruh Latihan Senam Hasil belajar Kebugaran jasmani (SKJ) Terhadap Tingkat Kebugaran Siswa Kelas V di MIN Donimulyo Kabupaten Malang. Al-Mudarris. *Journal Of Education*, 1(1), 22–29.
3. Arikunto, S. (2019). *Prosedur Penelitian: Suatu Pendekatan Praktik*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
4. Darmawan, I. (2017). Upaya Meningkatkan Hasil belajar Kebugaran jasmani Siswa Melalui Penjas. *Jurnal Inspirasi Pendidikan*, 7(2), 143–154.
5. Dwicahya, N., & Arjuna, F. (2017). Pengaruh Latihan Circuit Bodyweight Terhadap Hasil belajar Kebugaran jasmani, Indeks Massa Tubuh, Persentase Lemak Tubuh Dan Fleksibilitas Member Fitness Center Lotus Nusantara Bersinar Ros-In Hotel Yogyakarta. *Medikora*, 16(1), 3–15.
6. Erik, X., Ilahi, B. R., & others. (2023). Pengaruh latihan circuit traning daya tahan untuk meningkatkan kesegaran jasmani pemain sepakbola u-12 SSB abhiseva Bengkulu tengah: The effect of endurance circuit training exercises to improve the physical fitness of U-12 soccer players at SSB Abhiseva Bengkulu, Central Bengkulu. *SPORT GYMNASTICS: Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan Jasmani*, 4(1), 50–59.
7. Haeruddin, H., Nuheriana, A., & Agung, G. (2023). Upaya Meningkatkan Derajat Kebugaran Jasmani melalui Metode Sirkuit Training pada Siswa MA Annur Nusa. *ACADEMIA: Jurnal Inovasi Riset Akademik*, 3(4), 214–220.
8. Haryanto, A. I., Gani, A. A., Ramadan, G., Samin, G., Fataha, I., & Kadir, S. S. (2022). Body Mass Index Conditions of Running Athletes Before Ramadan. *JUARA: Jurnal Olahraga*, 7(1), 64–70.
9. Hudain, M. A., Suwardi, S., Nawir, N., Arimbi, A., & Risal, A. W. (2023). Pengaruh Metode Latihan Dan Koordinasi Mata Tangan Terhadap Keterampilan Dribling Dalam Permainan Bolabasket Pada Atlet Perbasi Kabupaten Bone. *Jurnal Review Pendidikan Dan Pengajaran (JRPP)*, 6(4), 2643–2654.
10. Kamaruddin, I., Nurhidayati, K., Stefanus Igolois, G., Uran, A. K., Wirda Ningsih, T. F., & others. (2022). Manajemen Pendidikan. *PT Global Eksekutif Teknologi*.
11. Kamaruddin, I., Suarni, E., Rambe, S., Sakti, B. P. S., Rachman, R. S., & Kurniadi, P. (2023). Penerapan model pembelajaran berbasis proyek dalam pendidikan: Tinjauan literatur. *Jurnal Review Pendidikan Dan Pengajaran (JRPP)*, 6(4), 2742–2747.
12. Lestari, P. D. J. P., Bahrozi, I., & Yuliana, I. (2023). Kompetensi pedagogik guru dalam pelaksanaan kurikulum merdeka. *Jurnal Review Pendidikan Dasar: Jurnal Kajian Pendidikan Dan Hasil Penelitian*, 9(3), 153–160.
13. Mohzana, M., Merla, M., Boari, Y., Hudain, M. A., & Kamaruddin, I. (2023). The Analysis Of The Effectiveness Of Group Investigation Method Implementation In Increasing Student Learning Outcomes. *Mudir: Jurnal Manajemen Pendidikan*, 5(1), 148–153.
14. Nahar, K., Nikmah, A. R., & Kriswandani, K. (2024). Pengaruh Model Problem Based Learning Berbantuan Geogebra Dan Teka Teki Silang (TTS) Terhadap Hasil Belajar Siswa Kelas Xi-4 Sma Negeri 3 Salatiga. *Jurnal Lebesgue: Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan Matematika, Matematika Dan*

Statistika, 5(3), 1539–1551.

15. Pulungan, N. R. P., Nasution, M. A., & Siregar, D. (2021). Pelaksanaan metode bin nazhar di Pondok Pesantren an-Nur Padangsidempuan. *Jurnal El-Thawalib*, 2(1), 1–14.
16. Purba, J., Widowati, A., & Daya, W. J. (2020). Peningkatan Kebugaran Jasmani Melalui Variasi Latihan Sirkuit Dan Olahraga Aerobik Pada Siswa-Siswi Kelas X Di Sman Titian Teras Jambi. *Jurnal Ilmu Keolahragaan*, 3(1), 10–16.
17. Rachmawati, A. (2015). Perbandingan Tingkat Kebugaran Jasmani Sekolah SMAN, MAN dengan SMKN (Studi Pada Siswa Kelas X di SMAN 1 Mojosari, Siswa Kelas X MAN Mojosari dan Siswa Kelas X di SMKN 1 Pungging). *Jurnal Pendidikan Olahraga Dan Kesehatan*, 3(3).
18. Sulistiyono, S., Primasoni, N., Rahayu, T. W., & Galih, D. (2022). The Relationship between Speed and Agility on the Football Skills of Young Football Players. *ACTIVE: Journal of Physical Education, Sport, Health and Recreation*, 11(1), 42–46.
19. Supariyadi, T., Mahfud, I., & Aguss, R. M. (2022). Hubungan Tingkat Kebugaran Jasmani Terhadap Prestasi Belajar Penjas Tahun 2021. *J. Arts Educ*, 2(2), 60–71.
20. Wibowo, P. (2018). *Perbedaan Metode Latihan Set System dan Circuit Training Terhadap Kebugaran Jasmani Peserta Ekstrakurikuler Bulutangkis SMP Negeri 2 Banguntapan*.